

Modelling Fire Service Response Times in West Midlands, UK

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Summary

This study examines the prediction of median fire response time of grid cells in West Midlands County, using supervised machine learning, including Lasso regression and tree-based models (Random Forest, XGBoost). Results show that random forest achieved the highest accuracy ($R^2 = 0.80$), with fire station distance and neighbouring fire frequency being the most important factors. This research has the potential to inform fire response strategies and fire station siting, in order to improve emergency preparedness.

KEYWORDS: Fire response time, Lasso regression, Random Forest, XGBoost.

1. Introduction

According to the World Fire Statistics report by the International Association of Fire and Rescue Services, in 2022, an estimated 19,600 people lost their lives due to fire-related incidents across 55 countries, highlighting the severe impact of fire hazards on communities worldwide (CTIF, 2024). Response time is a crucial element in the effectiveness of fire services, as shorter response times are strongly associated with reduced fire damage and increased survival rates (Challands, 2010; Jaldell, 2017). Consequently, minimising response time is a crucial objective to improve the service efficiency of fire departments, thereby to enhance community safety. In urban areas with complex spatial and socio-economic dynamics, optimising fire service response time remains a challenge.

Current methods for predicting fire service response times primarily rely on historical data and traditional statistical models. These approaches often use linear regression models or simple algorithms that assume a direct and stable relationship between variables, such as distance to the nearest fire station and response time (Buffington and Ezekoye, 2019). Moreover, traditional prediction models provide inadequate consideration of socio-economic factors and community-specific risks. Many existing models fail to sufficiently integrate variables such as income levels, population density, and the presence of vulnerable populations, which can lead to disparities in response time predictions across different regions (Kc, Ardianto and Wang, 2024).

In this study, we employ a 500-meter grid system to aggregate historical fire incident data, transitioning the research focus from predicting individual incident response times to examining spatial variations across the region. By applying Lasso regression and tree-based machine learning models, including Random Forest and XGBoost, we analyse the importance of different spatial, infrastructural, and socio-economic factors influencing fire response times.

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In the following, we describe the dataset used in Section 2 and the methods in Section 3. We then present the results in Section 4. Finally, we outline the future direction in Section 5.

2. Data

This study focuses on West Midlands County in the United Kingdom (UK). Located in the heart of England, West Midlands is a metropolitan and ceremonial county covering an area of approximately 902 square kilometres (Ordnance Survey, 2024). Figure 1 shows the geographical location of West Midlands County within UK. The historical fire incident data utilised in this study comprises all recorded fire-related events occurring between 2009 and 2023, which were obtained from the West Midlands Fire Service (WMFS). Table 1 provides a detailed description of the independent variables used in this work, including socioeconomic factors, physical infrastructure, fire services accessibility, and geographical and environmental features.

Figure 1 Location of the West Midlands (Ordnance Survey, 2024)

Table 1 Description of independent variables used in model training

Variable Type	Independent Variables	Description
Socioeconomic Factors	Total rented	Count of social and private dwellings that are rented.
	Elderly above 65 years	Count of people aged 65 and above.
	Children below 14 years	Count of people aged 14 and below.
	Socioeconomic disadvantage	Index of Multiple Deprivation.
Physical Infrastructure	Street connectivity	It is a link to node ratio - the total number of links (road segments between intersections) divided by the total number of nodes (intersections and dead-ends).

		Higher values signify higher street connectivity.
	Street network density	The total number of nodes or intersections, including dead ends divided. Higher values signify higher street network densities.
	Road density	The total street length. Higher values signify higher road densities.
	Buildings	Count of buildings.
Fire Services Accessibility	Fire station number	The number of fire stations within a specific distance.
	Distance to the fire station	Distance from the grid to the nearest fire station.
	Frequency of neighbouring fires	Frequency of neighbouring fires monthly.
Geographical and Environmental Features	Land use	The composition of land use within each grid.
	Points of interest	Count of points of interest of different categories.

3. Method

3.1. Data aggregation and feature processing

To facilitate the analysis of response times, the fire incident data were aggregated into 500-metre grid cells. The median of fire response time in each grid cell is used as the primary metric to evaluate the local fire service performance, where a shorter response time corresponds to a higher level of service performance.

A total of 13 independent variables was selected based on literature review (Kc and Corcoran, 2017) and practical considerations, including socioeconomic factors (e.g., population demographics, housing conditions, deprivation index), physical infrastructure (e.g., street connectivity, road density, building counts), fire service accessibility (e.g., fire station proximity, historical fire frequency), and geographical and environmental features (e.g., land use, points of interest).

3.2. Model selection and training

Predictive models were developed using both Lasso regression and tree-based methods, including random forest and XGBoost. The models were evaluated using R^2 and MSE, and then we used the feature importance of random forest to identify key determinants of response times.

4. Results and analysis

4.1. Predictive performance of median fire response time

Lasso regression and tree-based models (random forest and XGBoost) were evaluated using R^2 and MSE. Among these three methods, random forest achieved the highest predictive accuracy, with an R^2 value of 0.80, indicating a strong ability to explain the variance in fire response times. XGBoost and Lasso regression also showed competitive performance, with R^2 values of 0.76 and 0.77,

respectively. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the grid-based approach in capturing spatial patterns of fire response times.

Table 2. The R^2 and MSE of Lasso regression, Random Forest and XGBoost on the test set

Model	R^2	MSE
Lasso Regression	0.77	3534.28
Random Forest	0.80	3076.51
XGBoost	0.76	3590.28

4.2. Important factors affecting fire response time

For the random forest model, which yielded the best model performance, the top five important features were identified as distance to the fire station, frequency of neighbouring fires, children below 14 years, road density, and elderly above 65 years.

Figure 2 Top five features importance by Random Forest Model

It is evident that as the distance to the nearest fire station increases, the fire response time significantly increases, which aligns with common sense and findings in the literature (Jusoh et al., 2023). In contrast, an increase in the frequency of neighbouring fires likely indicates higher fire risk in the area. One possible reason is that the frequency of neighbouring fires might reflect higher urban density, where fire stations are more strategically positioned, thus enabling faster response times. This interpretation provides a plausible explanation for the observed pattern, although further research would be necessary to empirically verify this hypothesis.

5. Future directions

Future research would validate the relationship between fire frequency, urban density, and fire station distribution to better understand their impact on response times. Additionally, the predictive modelling could be explored to enhance the accuracy of fire risk assessment and optimise response times.

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